

Appendix A: Information Sheet and Consent Form

General Information/Background

Hello! My name is **Mbele Whiteson**, a Student at the University of Ghana studying Master of Science in applied health social science. I am conducting a study on the acceptability of COVID-19 vaccination among healthcare workers in Ayawaso West Municipality.

Procedure

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to fill in a questionnaire that will take approximately 20 minutes to complete.

Risks and Discomforts

There are minimal risks associated with participation in this study. You may feel uncomfortable answering some questions, but there are no known physical or psychological risks.

Benefits

The benefits of participating in this study include contributing to the understanding of determinants of acceptability of COVID-19 vaccination among healthcare workers, and this information will aid in the formulation of targeted campaigns to promote vaccine uptake.

Confidentiality and anonymity

Your participation in this study will be kept confidential. Results from this study may be published and the data set deposited in a public repository. However, your name or any identifying information will not be used in any publication or presentation resulting from this study.

Right to refuse or withdraw

Your participation in this study is voluntary and your decision not to be part of the study will not affect your relationship with the staff of the Ghana Health Service in any way. You will also not lose any benefits that you would have otherwise been entitled. If you agree to take part in the study, you can still withdraw from the study at any time, and this will not affect you in any way.

Are you willing to participate in the survey? 1. Yes [] 2. No []